

ISSN No. : XXXX-XXXX
Volume : 01
Issue : 01
DOI :

Publisher

ROGANIDAN VIKRUTIVIGYAN PG ASSOCIATION

Reg. No. : MAHA-703/16(NAG)

Year of Establishment – 2016

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DIAGNOSTICS AND RESEARCH

Critical Analysis of Concept of Biomarkers from Ayurveda Perspective

Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule¹, Dr. Uday V. Chougule²

1. Associate Professor and HOD, Dept. of Roganidan and Vikruti Vigyan,
Manjushree Research Institute of Ayurvedic Science, Gandhinagar, Gujarat -382610, India

2. Associate Professor, Dept. of Ras Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana,
Manjushree Research Institute of Ayurvedic Science, Gandhinagar, Gujarat -382610, India

Corresponding author : Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule Citation : -

Article Info : Published on : 14/07/2023

Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule¹, Dr. Uday V. Chougule² Critical Analysis of Concept of Biomarkers from Ayurveda Perspective, Inter.J.Diagnostics & Research1(1)2023IJDRMSID0003.

ABSTRACT

Today's era of globalization has introduced Ayurveda on a global platform like never before. Ayurveda is the ancient life science which aims at leading a healthy life but diseases form an inseparable part of life. All these altered conditions are diagnosed most of the times on basis of clinical features as per ayurveda samhitas. With development of technology the contemporary science uses various biomolecules, imaging techniques in addition to clinical features to diagnose a condition, understand its pathophysiology, monitor the intervention or treatment outcome, these are called as biomarkers. It is necessary for ayurveda scholars to get acquainted with this new glossary to face challenges of globalization. In this review article the literature study of modern concept of biomarkers has been made and an attempt is made to envision biomarkers examples mentioned in ayurveda literature. Owing to the vastness of Ayurveda literature its relevance with modern classification of biomarkers is explained with only a few examples. The article aims at giving ayurveda scholars scientific vision while studying ayurveda without losing the core of ayurveda fundamental principles and willingness to incorporate contemporary biomolecular and imaging techniques advances.

Keywords : Biomarker, Upamaan Praman, Ayurveda

INTRODUCTION

Diseases have been a part of life since time immemorial and continuous efforts are being made to understand the disease process in better way aiming at better intervention and therapeutics results. Ayurveda the most ancient science of life has explained the concepts of disease and treatment in short as Trisutra viz., Hetu, Linga, Aushada skanda further elaborating it into Nidan Panchak viz., Nidan, Purvarupa, Rupa, Upashay and Samprapti ^[1]. On the other hand, the modern medical science explains the disease process in four aspects viz.,

etiology - its cause, pathogenesis - the mechanisms of its development, morphologic changes - the structural alterations induced in the cells and organs of the body, and clinical significance - the functional consequences of the morphologic changes ^[2]. All these aspects can be measured using various biomarkers. The term "biomarker" ("biological marker") includes a broad subcategory of medical signs – which are objective indications of medical state as observed from outside the patient that can be reproduced and measured accurately ^[3].

AIM

Understand the concept of biomarkers and analyze its relevance from Ayurveda perspective.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Classical texts and modern literature is reviewed and critically analyzed to put forth logical interpretation in context to biomarkers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Biomarker Working Group- BEST (Biomarkers, Endpoints, and other Tools) Resource defines biomarker as a characteristic that is measured as an indicator of normal biological processes, pathogenic processes, or biological responses to an exposure or intervention, including therapeutic interventions. Biomarkers may be any characteristics – physiologic, molecular, histological or radiographic, but does not measure subjective characteristics like how an individual feels, functions, or survives [4].

Thus, proper identification of biomarkers in human body especially for personalized medicine, disease diagnosis, and prognosis is clinically very important [5].

The concept of biomarker was defined as “a functional variant or quantitative index of a biological process that predicts or reflects the evolution of or predisposition to a disease or a response to a therapy” by Fitzgerald and colleagues in 2016 earlier [6]. Biomarker is a distinguished bio-molecule with the ability to play a prime role in different biological and pathological processes or gives a specific pharmacological response to a drug, giving apt information about body’s actual condition [7].

Ideal biomarker :

An ideal biomarker must possess certain qualities mentioned in fig.1 [8, 9].

Figure1. Ideal biomarker - Characteristics.

Based on Genetic & molecular biology method	Based on Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type 0, • Type 1, • Type 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Molecular, • Histologic, • Radiographic, • Physiological Characteristics

Based on Applications- Disease related	Based on Biomolecule
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Susceptibility • Diagnostic, • Prognostic, • Safety • Predictive, • Monitoring • Response 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNA marker, • RNA marker, • Protein based , • Lipid Based, • Sugar based

Classification of Biomarkers :

The biomarkers can be classified on various parameters: fig 2.

Figure 2. Biomarker Types Based on Various Parameters

A. Biomarker Types Based on Genetic and Molecular Biology Method:

a. Type 0 - Natural history markers: A natural history marker of a disease that correlates longitudinally and is used to represent clinical indices. Examples -

i. Raised ESR value in Aamvata [10].

ii. Bio-markers of Vardhakya (ageing) like those which determine the biological age i.e. skin elasticity and visual accommodation, those which predict the remaining life expectancy i.e. DHEA-S and hand-grip power, those which determine disease susceptibility, i.e. systolic BP and glucose tolerance test. All these bio-markers can be classified as laboratory tests (eg. blood and urine tests) or as physical tests carried out in a clinic [11].

b. Type 1 - Drug activity markers: A marker used to explain the effect of a therapeutic intervention according to its mechanism/ mode of action. E.g.

i. Use of Terminal Deoxynucleotidyl transferase – mediated dUTP nick end labeling assay (TUNNEL), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 (ALDH1) to analyze breast cancer chemoprevention effect of Ashwagandha (Withania Somnifera) [12].

c. Type 2 - Surrogate markers: A marker (surrogate end point) which is intended to substitute for a clinical end point. It is expected to predict clinical benefit or lack of benefit on the basis of various parameters like - epidemiology, pathophysiological, therapeutic, or other scientific evidence [13]. Example-

i. Traditional Ayurvedic doctors used ants for the identification of “sweet urine” in patients [14].

B. Based on characteristics: Figure 3
Figure 3. Biomarker Types Based on Characteristics

C. Based on disease related application – Table 1.

Many of the biomarkers can fall in more than one category based on its application made.

Table 1. Biomarkers classification based on disease related application.

SR. NO.	BIOMARKER TYPE	EXAMPLES
1)	Diagnostic biomarker is used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To detect or confirm presence of a disease or condition of interest or - To identify individuals with a subtype of the disease ^[4]. 	Diagnostic biomarker to identify patients with chronic kidney disease - Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) may be used ^[15] . <i>Pratyatma lakshanas</i> of diseases e.g <i>Haridra Netra Mutra Twak</i> in <i>Kamala</i> , <i>Gudena Atidravasaranam</i> in <i>Atiasaara</i> ^[16] .
2)	Monitoring biomarker is measured repeatedly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For assessing status of a disease or medical condition or - For evidence of exposure to (or effect of) a medical product or an environmental agent ^[4]. 	For assessing whether the desired effect of anticoagulation has been attained in patients on warfarin - International normalized ratio (INR) or prothrombin time (PT) may be used as monitoring biomarkers ^[17] . Assessment of ESR value in <i>Aamavat</i> treatment ^[10] .
3)	Response biomarker is used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To show that a biological response either potentially beneficial or harmful, has happened in an individual who has been administered a medical product or exposed to an environmental agent ^[4]. a. Pharmacodynamic biomarker: A response biomarker that shows biologic activity of a medical product or environmental agent. But it does not necessarily reach conclusions about efficacy or 	When evaluating a patient's response to warfarin treatment for prevention of thrombosis - International normalized ratio (INR) may be used as a pharmacodynamic biomarker ^[18] . Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol reduction is a validated surrogate endpoint for reduction of cardiovascular events and has been used as the basis for ayurvedic herbal anti-hypercholestromlaemia preparations ^[19] .

<p>Response biomarker is used</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To show that a biological response either potentially beneficial or harmful, has happened in an individual who has been administered a medical product or exposed to an environmental agent ^[4]. <p>a. Pharmacodynamic biomarker: A response biomarker that shows biologic activity of a medical product or environmental agent. But it does not necessarily reach conclusions about efficacy or disease outcome or necessarily link this activity to an established mechanism/mode of action ^[4].</p> <p>b. Surrogate endpoint biomarker: A response biomarker that serves as a substitute/representative for direct measure of how a patient feels, functions, or survives and is used as endpoint in clinical trials ^[4].</p>	<p>When evaluating a patient’s response to warfarin treatment for prevention of thrombosis - International normalized ratio (INR) may be used as a pharmacodynamic biomarker ^[18].</p> <p>Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol reduction is a validated surrogate endpoint for reduction of cardiovascular events and has been used as the basis for ayurvedic herbal anti-hypercholestromia preparations ^[19].</p>
<p>Predictive biomarker is used</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To identify individuals who are more likely to experience a favorable or unfavorable effect 	<p>When evaluating women with platinum-sensitive ovarian cancer - Breast Cancer genes 1 and 2 (BRCA1/2) mutations may be used as predictive biomarkers ^[4].</p>

D. Based on biomolecule [27]

? DNA- based biomarker

? RNA- based biomarker

? Protein based biomarker

? Lipid based biomarker

? Sugar based biomarker

DISCUSSION

Ayurveda is a holistic science which has basic principles like equilibrium in the components of body like Dosha, Dhātu, Mala, Agni affect the functioning of various srotasas (different systems) and maintain health of an individual. Their normal status or any deflection in the normal status is manifested in form of lakshanas (clinical signs and symptoms). Trividha pariksha (Darshan, Sparshana, Prashna), Shadvidha Pariksha (panch jnanendriya pariksha and prashna pariksha) have been explained in Bruhatrayees to assess the status of a person and disease. Selection of treatment is based on samprapti (pathogenesis) occurred in patient and cause for particular samprapti. Efficacy of treatment is also evaluated in terms of samprapti vighatana (reversal of disease condition) which is evident by alleviation of the clinical features manifested. These clinical features encompass both clinical endpoints and biomarkers. Clinical endpoints are variables that reflect or characterize how a subject in a study or clinical trial “feels, functions, or survives”. They are, in other words, variables that represent a study subject's health and wellbeing from the subject's perspective. On other hand the contemporary medical science more emphasis is given on biomolecular, radiological or imaging investigations to explore and understand the diseases, analyze treatment efficacy or adverse effects, these are included under the umbrella term “Biomarker”. In the last five decades the definition of biomarker used has seen many changes in accordance with scientific and clinical progress. Though the term “Biomarker” is used since 1973, before that it was referenced as “Biochemical marker”. Though the term biomarker may be new, the concept isn't de nova to ayurveda - biomarkers mentioned are in form of lakshanas and used as objective criterias. Upamaan, Pratyaksha, Anumaan pramaan are used for biomarkers explanation. It has been observed that the ancient acharyas have tried to explain the complex concepts of pathophysiology and clinical features using upamana pramana (similes used). We find innumerable examples of similes given in Bruhatrayees and Laghutrayees to

explain various signs and symptoms too. The bases of biomarkers in Ayurveda are panch arthas- Shabda, Sparsha, Rupa, Gandha, Rasa.

1) Shabda – (Sound as parameter)

? Changes in voice of a patient like Kapot iva kujanam (stridor) in apatantraka patient. – can be used as diagnostic marker.

? Abnormal sounds heard by physician in patient – crepitus in joints of Sandhigata vata patient – can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.

2) Sparsha – (Palpable parameters)

? Kathina sparsha in case of Vataj Vrana - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.

? Vatapurna druti sparsha in Vatodar - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.

3) Rupa – (Visible parameters)

? Varna (colour) – yellowish discolouration of nails, eyes in liver disorders - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.

? Sansthan (clinical features) - Inflammation at joints in arthritic conditions can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.

? Rajjanma (caput medusae) in ascitis - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.

? Praman – liver and spleen enlargement in yakrutodar (hepatomegaly) and pleehodar (splenomegaly) respectively etc. can be used as monitoring marker, response marker.

4) Rasa – (Taste as parameter) Use of various animals is mentioned to interpret indirectly the changes in body fluids of patient.

? Use of ants to analyze urine sugar content can be used as diagnostic marker, predictive marker, response marker.

? Use of dogs and crow to differentiate between shuddha rakta and Raktapitta.- can be used as diagnostic marker, predictive marker, prognostic marker.

5) Gandha – (Smell as parameter)

? Various examples are given in Charak samhita, indriya sthan 2nd chapter related to smell emitted by patient- can be used prognostic markers.

Ayurveda literature is full of clinical knowledge and combined with integrated modern biomarker vision will help enhance the scientificness of research and practice. The proper interpretation of these parameters in accordance with the basic principles of Ayurveda can enrich understanding and application of ayurveda concepts. The biomarkers can be used for

- Diagnosing stage of disease
- Prognosis of a disease
- Selection of treatment modality
- Assess treatment efficacy
- Assess ADRs, Toxicity

In clinical settings the disease often has multifactorial etiology which can in turn have innumerable various pathways to exhibit a disease. Treatment outcomes also have variability in respect to doctor- patient relationship, food habits, lifestyle variations from person to person, climate changes, demography, epigenetics posing challenges to select a biomarker. Judicious selection and assessment of appropriate biomarkers will benefit overall patient care.

CONCLUSION

- The term biomarker includes objective parameters in clinical setting along with laboratory and imaging investigations.
- Understanding the relationship between measurable biological processes and clinical outcomes is vital.
- Limited information about the types of processes involved in normal physiology of a biological process or pathophysiology of diseases makes constant reevaluation of biomarkers as surrogate endpoints essential.
- Use of biomarkers in Clinical practice & Studies (at least for retrospective analysis of biomarker correlation success) should always have clinical outcomes as ultimate measures, to maximize benefits to patients and reduce harm.
- Use of Clinical findings as Biomarkers and/ or Laboratory and Imaging Biomarkers should be made judiciously for person's/ patient's benefit.

REFERENCES

- 1.Kasinath Sastri, Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Charak Samhita of Agnivesh, Sutra Sthan Chp. 1/ 24 and Nidan sthan Chp.1/6. 1st edition, Varanasi; Choukhambha Bharati Academy; 2001: pg 8 and pg 601.
- 2.Vinay Kumar, Abul K. Abbas, Nelson Fausto.Robbins and Cotran Pathologic Basis Of Disease, 7th ed., Elsevier ; 2005:4
- 3.Kyle Strimbu and Jorge A. Tavel, M.D. Curr Opin HIV AIDS. 2010 November; 5(6): 463–466. doi:10.1097/COH.0b013e32833ed177

- 4.Biomarker Working Group F-N. BEST (Biomarkers, Endpoints, and other Tools) Resource. In: Spring S, editor. BEST (Biomarkers, Endpoints, and other Tools) Resource. Silver Spring (MD): FDA-NIH (2016).
- 5.Chen, X., Ba, Y., Ma, L. et al. Characterization of microRNAs in serum: a novel class of biomarkers for diagnosis of cancer and other diseases. Cell Research 2008; 18: 997.
- 6.García-Gutierrez MS, Navarrete F, Sala F, Gasparian A, Austrich-Olivares A and Manzanares J Biomarkers in Psychiatry: Concept, Definition, Types and Relevance to the Clinical Reality. Front. Psychiatry 2020; 11:432. doi: 10.3389/fpsyt.2020.00432.
- 7.Atkinson, A.J. Jr., Colburn, W.A., DeGruttola, V.G. et al. Biomarkers and surrogate endpoints: preferred definitions and conceptual framework. Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics 2001; 69: 89–95.
- 8.Sahu P, Pinkalwar N, Dubey RD, Paroha S, Chatterjee S, Chatterjee T. Biomarkers: An Emerging Tool for Diagnosis of a Disease and Drug Development. Asian J Res Pharm Sci 2011; 1: 9-16.
- 9.<https://www.library.yorku.ca/find/Record/2523694>
- 10.P. Pandey, S. Rastogi, A. Lawrence et al, Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine 2023; 14(2).100689; 1-9 : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaim.2023.100689>
- 11.S.M.S. Samarakoon, H.M. Chandola. Some biomarkers of ageing in Ayurvedic perspective, Indian Journal of Ancient Medicine and Yoga; Volume 2 Number 4, October -December 2009, 197-210
- 12.Suman K.S and others, Disease subtype – Independent biomarkers of breast cancer chemoprevention by the Ayurvedic Medicine Phytochemical Withaferin A. J Natl Cancer Inst. 2016 Dec 31; 109(6): djw293. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djw293. PMID: 28040797; PMCID: PMC5928779.
- 13.Elizabeth A Yetley, David L DeMets and William R Harlan Jr. Surrogate disease markers as substitutes for chronic disease outcomes in studies of diet and chronic disease relations; Am J Clin Nutr 2017;106:1175–89.

14. Van der Greef, J. & Smilde, A.K. Symbiosis of chemometrics and metabolomics: past, present, and future. *J. Chemometrics* 2005;19; 376–386.
15. Garcia-Gutierrez MS, Navarrete F, Sala F, Gasparyan A, Austrich-Olivares A and Manzanares J. Biomarkers in Psychiatry: Concept, Definition, Types and Relevance to the Clinical Reality. *Front. Psychiatry* 2020; 11:432. doi: 10.3389/fpsyt.2020.00432.
16. National Kidney Foundation. K/DOQI Clinical Practice Guidelines for Chronic Kidney Disease: Evaluation, Classification and Stratification. *Am J Kidney Dis* 39:S1-S266, 2002 (suppl 1). Accessed Dec 2016. Available at: https://www.kidney.org/sites/default/files/docs/ckd_evaluation_classification_stratification.pdf
17. Monika Gupta, Gopikrishna S. An Appraisal on Biomarkers in Ayurveda. *J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci* 2019; 4 (2):137-139.
18. Holbrook A, Schulman S, Witt DM, Vandvik PO, Fish J, Kovacs MJ, Svensson PJ, Veenstra DL, Crowther M, Guyatt GH. Evidence-based management of anticoagulant therapy: Antithrombotic Therapy and Prevention of Thrombosis, 9th ed: American College of Chest Physicians Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Chest*. 2012 Feb; 141(2) Suppl: e152S–e184S. PubMed PMID: 22315259.
19. Dinesh Gyawali, Robert H Schneider, David W Orme-Johnson and Sridharan Ramaratnam. Ayurvedic herbal preparations for hypercholesterolaemia. *Cochrane database Syst Rev*. 2019; 2019(3): CD012076. Published online 2019 Mar 15. Doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD012076.pub2
20. Apoorva Jnana, Thokur Sreepathy Murali and others. Prakriti phenotypes as a stratifier of gut microbiome: A new frontier in personalized medicine?. *J Ayurveda Integr Med*. 2020 Jul-Sep; 11(3):360-365. PubMed PMID: 32718805.
21. Basu NN, Ingham S, Hodson J, Lalloo F, Bulman M, Howell A, Evans DG. Risk of contralateral breast cancer in BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutation carriers: a 30-year semi-prospective analysis. *Fam Cancer*. 2015 Dec; 14(4):531–8. doi: 10.1007/s10689-015-9825-9. PubMed PMID: 26239694.
22. Lakshmi Prati Shastri. Yogaratnakara with vaidyaprabha hindi commentary, Purvardha, Mutrapariksha, Verse 11-22, first ed. Varanasi: Choukhamba Prakashan: 2015; pg 10-11
23. Kasinath Sastri, Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Charak Samhita of Agnivesh, Indriya Sthan Chp. 1-12. 1st edition, Varanasi; Choukhambha Bharati Academy; 2001; pg 965-1024.
24. Wasung ME, Chawla LS, Madero M. Biomarkers of renal function, which and when? *Clin Chim Acta*. 2015 Jan 1; 438:350–7. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2014.08.039. PubMed PMID: 25195004.
25. C.Y. Jagtap and others. Acute And subchronic Toxicity Study of Tamra Bhasma (incinerated copper) prepared from Ashodita (unpurified) and Shodita (Purified) Tamra in Rats. *Indian J Pharm Sci*. 2013 May–Jun; 75(3):346-352. Doi: 10.4103/0250-474X.117433. PubMed PMID: 24082351
26. Struwing JP, Hartge P, Wacholder S, Baker SM, Berlin M, McAdams M, Timmerman MM, Brody LC, Tucker MA. The risk of cancer associated with specific mutations of BRCA1 and BRCA2 among Ashkenazi Jews. *N Engl J Med*. 1997 May 15; 336(20):1401–8. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199705153362001. PubMed PMID: 9145676
27. Ayesha Taj, Abdul Rehman, and Sadia Z. Bajwa. Biomarkers and Their Role in Detection of Biomolecules, published on 14 February 2020. Available on <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9783527345137.ch4>

ISSN No. : xxxx-xxxx

DOI :

Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule Inter. J.Digno. & Research

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License

Submission Link : <http://www.ijdrindia.com>**Benefits of Publishing with us**

Fast peer review process

Global archiving of the articles

Unrestricted open online access

Author retains copyright

Unique DOI for all articles

<https://ijdrindia.com>